

Enhancement Of Learning Performance Of Future German Language Teachers Through Challenge Learning

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Abstract: *The article discusses the nature, content, basic concepts and categories of problem-based teaching and its role in increasing the knowledge activity of students in the system of higher professional education.*

Keywords — Concept of problem-based learning, cognitive activity, cognitive difficulties, problem situation, problem, problem-based task, problem-based presentation lecture, problem-based teaching lecture, joint problem-based lecture, problem-based seminar session classes.

INTRODUCTION.

On the basis of the reforms carried out in the field of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the education of young people, who are today and tomorrow of our country, as mature professionals, is being promoted as an urgent issue. The result of the reforms implemented in the education system of our country in the "Concept of Higher Education Development until 2030" in the Republic of Uzbekistan in directing the national education system to achieve a new result is "a new system of universal knowledge, skills, qualifications, as well as the experience of independent activity and personal responsibility of learners, that is, modern basic it is stated that it serves as "competencies".

Regarding the analysis of the pedagogical-psychological aspects of the development of educational competence of German language teachers as a pedagogical concept, we will first analyze our approach by referring to the scientific opportunities in the works of local and foreign researchers.

The essence of problem-based teaching is the teacher's management of students' cognitive activities to acquire new knowledge by creating a problem situation in their educational work and solving educational tasks, problems and questions. This creates a scientific-research method of acquiring knowledge.

Problem-based education is a method of teaching the educational material in a way that creates cognitive tasks and problems based on scientific research in the student's mind.

Problematic situations arise in the student's thinking activity, and they encourage the child to objectively search and draw logically correct scientific conclusions.

A problem is a subjective form of expressing the need to develop scientific knowledge.

It is a conflict that objectively arises between knowledge and ignorance in a problematic situation, that is, in the process of social development.

A problem situation is a certain mental state of the student. Such a situation arises due to the realization of conflicts in the process of performing certain tasks (solving a problem, finding an answer to a question).

Realizing this conflict makes students want to search for new knowledge about the method or conditions of doing the work.

Every teacher working in the educational system must first clearly understand the following sequence in order to apply the problem-based learning method in the course of the lesson.

The problem-based learning method is implemented as follows:

- ✓ pose a problem;
- ✓ studying the conditions characterizing the problem;
- ✓ solving the problem;
- ✓ justification of the correctness of the found solution;
- ✓ appeared in the process of searching for a solution to the problem
- ✓ understanding of new knowledge;
- ✓ systematization, motivation and generalization of the problem;
- ✓ to study the solution of the problem, to look for its more compact and convenient ways.
- ✓ All work on educational technology has its own practical basis. The preparation of the educational project predetermines the activities that the teacher and the student will carry out together in the future.

In the implementation of the educational project, the teacher should, first of all, consider the creation of problem situations that stimulate the student's thinking to draw logically correct, scientific conclusions and master them.

One of the main rules of the competence approach in education is the understanding of competence as a subjective quality of a person. It is manifested in pedagogical conditions such as the collective nature of educational activities and the

assimilation of knowledge through strict social factors, the development of skills and competencies in students depending on the subjective motivations of studying, the attitude to the subject of study, the abilities and experience of the learner. For this reason, the qualities that affect the personality of the student through the pedagogical conditions of the development of the educational and cognitive competence of German language teachers in the educational system of the development of educational and cognitive competence of pre-service military education teachers are considered an urgent issue.

As we dwell on the content-essence of the pedagogical-psychological aspects of the concept of the development of educational and cognitive competence of German language teachers: it is necessary to dwell on the etymological analysis of the concepts of "competence", "competence". Scientists have interpreted the concepts of "competence" and "competence" differently. Competency approach means, first of all, the word "Competence" comes from the word "to compete", which means "knowledge in this or that field".

In the development of the science of pedagogy, research on the analysis of these concepts has begun not only in the world, but also by the scientists of our country, and researches have been conducted on competences and competences for various types of activity.

In conclusion, in today's modern conditions, the use of problem-based educational technologies ensures the effective progress of the educational process and, at the same time, develops the student's ability to think independently, critically and creatively. As a result of active independent activity of students, it allows creative acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities and development of mental activity. Also, if the educational processes of students are organized by the pedagogue, realizing the essence of problem-based education, i.e., problem-based teaching, he organizes management of their cognitive activities by acquiring new knowledge by solving problems, obstacles and situations. This creates a scientific-research method of acquiring knowledge.

Purposeful and effective use of problematic educational technologies by the teacher in the process of teaching is the basis for improving the quality of education and increasing its effectiveness.

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